

chain in phosphorous moiety increases, enzyme inhibition decreases. Compounds having propyl substitution at 'R' are better inhibitors as compared to the ethyl substituted in the phosphorous side chain. Thus in the phosphorous side chain, the order of inhibitory action against acetylcholinesterase is Me > Pr > Et > Bu.

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4-NN-Bis-2'-Carboxyethylaminobenzaldehyde as Spray Reagent for Acyl Glycines in Paper Chromatography

V. S. JOLLY* and A. K. SHRIVASTAVA

Department of Chemistry, Maharaja College, Chhatarpur-471 001

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FORMATION of highly coloured azlactones prompted the use of aromatic aldehydes as reagent for acyl glycines¹⁻³. The present note reports the synthesis of 4-NN-bis-2'-carboxyethylaminobenzaldehyde (*bis*-CEAB) which on condensation with acyl glycines gave deep coloured 2-substituted phenyl-4-(4'-NN-bis-β-carboxyethylaminobenzylidene)-5-oxazolones(I).

Data concerning the new products are set out in the Table I.

The use of *bis*-CEAB as spray reagent for acyl glycines has been explored. The sensitivity of *bis*-CEAB is good and the colour produced are generally intense and stable.

Experimental

Synthesis of acyl glycines⁴⁻⁶ and of oxazolones (I)¹⁻³ was accomplished as reported in literature. Uncorrected m.p.s. are reported.

4-NN-Bis-2'-carboxyethylaminobenzaldehyde (*bis*-CEAB) :

4-NN-Bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzaldehyde⁷ (10.0 g) and aq. sodium hydroxide (100 ml, 10%) was refluxed for one hr. and the solution was neutralised with conc. sulphuric acid (9.4 ml, density 1.84) when *bis*-CEAB precipitated. It was filtered under suction and recrystallised from water; m.p. 141; yield, 8.2 g. (70.7%). Found: C, 58.3; H, 5.98; N, 5.56; C₁₈H₁₅O₅N requires C, 58.8; H, 5.66 and N, 5.28% IR(KBr) shows peaks at 1730 and 1690 cm⁻¹ (C=O) and at 1320 cm⁻¹ (tert. amino gr.). 2 : 4-Dinitrophenyl hydrazone prepared by usual methods, m.p. 210°.

One per cent solution of *bis*-CEAB in acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate was found

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA ON 2-SUBSTITUTED PHENYL-4-(4'-NN-Bis- β -CARBOXYETHYLAMINO-BENZYLIDENE)-5-OXAZOLONES(I)

Sl. No.	R	Colour	Colour of the spots	m.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Mol. Formula	%N	
							Found	Calcd.
1.	H	Orange	Orange	226	67.2	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₂	6.81	6.86
2.	Cl(o-)	Bright yellow	Yellow	231	40.9	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ O ₆ N ₂ Cl	6.41	6.33
3.	Cl(p-)	Yellow	Yellow	234	47.7	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ O ₆ N ₂ Cl	6.39	6.33
4.	NO ₂ (o-)	Orange yellow	Orange yellow	248	35.5	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ O ₆ N ₃	9.71	9.29
5.	NO ₂ (p-)	Deep yellow	Deep yellow	256	48.8	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ O ₆ N ₃	9.79	9.29
6.	Cl(2)NO ₂ (5)	Yellow	Yellow	238	33.2	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ O ₆ N ₂ Cl	8.41	8.62
7.	Cinnamoyl	Red	Red	240	44.5	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₆ N ₂	6.84	6.45

effective in producing different colours from yellow to red with acyl glycines on paper.

The colours of the spots have been given in the Table I.

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Studies on Biologically Active Agents : Synthesis of Variously Substituted N¹-(4-substituted phenoxy acetyl/benzoyl secondary amines)-N²-Substituted Aryl Thioureas as Possible CNS, Anticonvulsant and MAO Inhibitory Agents

J. S. SHUKLA* and I. AHMAD

Department of Chemistry, Lucknow University,
Lucknow (India)

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SUBSTITUTED thioureas are known to possess pharmacodynamic properties¹⁻⁴. The present communication describes the synthesis of thiourea derivatives by incorporating heterocyclic moiety in

the hope that resulting product may have higher biological activities.

These substituted thioureas have been prepared by the condensation of *p*-nitro phenoxy and *p*-nitro-benzoyl chloride with secondary amine. Nitro group was reduced and then reacted with aryl isothiocyanate to obtain the desired product. Some of them were screened, which showed encouraging results.

Experimental

Synthesis of p-nitro phenoxy acetyl/benzoyl secondary amines :

They were prepared according to the method of Baker *et al*⁵. Melting points of *p*-nitro phenoxy acetyl and benzoyl dicyclohexylamine were found to be 302° and 200° respectively.

Synthesis of p-amino phenoxy acetyl/benzoyl secondary amines :

They were prepared by the method of Richard and Furst⁶. They are shown in Table 1.

Synthesis of N¹-(4-substituted phenoxy acetyl/benzoyl amines)-N²-substituted aryl thioureas :

They were prepared according to the method reported by George *et al*⁷. Arylisothiocyanate (0.01 mole) was added to a solution of *p*-amino-phenoxyacetyl or *p*-aminobenzoyl secondary amine (0.01 mole) in ethyl alcohol (25 ml). The mixture was heated under reflux for 4 hours. A solid mass was obtained, which was filtered and crystallized from suitable solvents. They are given in Table 1.

Elemental analyses of C, N and H were found within $\pm 0.5\%$ of theoretical and calculated values.

Pharmacological studies :

Toxicity studies : Acute toxicity study was performed with substituted thioureas. These compounds were administered intraperitoneally in albino mice and their approximate LD₅₀ were determined by conventional procedure⁸.